

Swimming of microorganisms at low Reynolds number flows; physics and applications by Farhad Jalilian

1. Introduction to bacterial structure and the mechanisms of bacterial motion

Bacterial motion in viscous fluids is an important topic in many fields as it influences biological processes that are involved in different fields such as mammalian reproduction, marine life ecosystem, and drug delivery applications [1]. Many types of bacteria are able to swim. The driving motivation for bacterial motion is the difference in nutrient concentration in different areas. Bacteria can sense nutrients by a process called chemotaxis and move towards the areas with higher concentration of nutrients and fewer concentrations of toxic materials. However, they do not use the same mechanism as what human being use to swim. We swim by creating a forward momentum, the requirement of which is the maintenance of the first half's displacement followed by the second half of the motion [2]. This mechanism, however, is not employed by micro-organisms in micro scale, and the means by which they swim is completely different.

Most kinds of bacteria perform motility. Motility of bacteria is a self-propelled motion, also known as locomotion. There are three main mechanisms for bacteria to exhibit motility. The first, and the most important and common mechanism is called flagellum motion, which is achieved by movement of flagella. Flagella is a rigid whip-like structure that is 20 nanometers in diameter and 15-20 microns in length and protrudes out from the surface of the cell. In order to have a sense of the thickness of flagella, it can be said that a single human hair is typically 4000 times thicker than flagella. Based upon the number of flagella that a cell has different types of cells can be differentiated. For example, a specific type of bacteria called monotrichous has one flagellum on its end. Some bacteria, called amphitrichous, have two flagella on both ends. If the bacteria's flagella are scattered all over the surface of the bacteria, then the bacteria is called peritrichous. For example, *E. coli* is a peritrichous type of bacteria. Flagella is a lash-like appendage, like a hollow cylinder, that contains a protein called flagellin. Flagellin forms a filament attached to a curved structure. Flagellin drives a rotary force originating from the proteinaceous rings that are in the cell wall. The filament rotates with a speed of 200 to more than 1000 revolution per second. The cylindrical slope of flagella helps the motion of micro-organism, also known as cell motility. Scientists have found that the direction of the flagellum rotation controls the bacterial movement. This is to say the direction of motion can be changed or even reversed instantaneously due to alteration of the position of a protein in the rotor. The expression that is used for

bacterial movement is known as “run and tumble”. When flagella rotate clockwise, the bacteria run, and when flagella rotate counter-clockwise, the bacteria tumbles [3]. We will see in the next chapters what reasons make bacteria capable for instantaneous moves.

Figure 1 derived from Wikipedia shows a section view of flagella. The filament is connected to a hook which is also connected to the proteinaceous rings underneath the cell membrane. The rings are connected to the rotary motor.

Another possible mechanism for bacterial motility is performed by a spiral filament. In this mechanism, the cell moves like a corkscrew. These bacteria have an axial filament that enables them to rotate spirally. Some other bacteria exhibit gliding motility. This mechanism and the reasons behind it are not well understood yet. However, it can be seen that the cell does not use flagella for its motility [3].

According to characteristics and calculations regarding bacterial locomotion, it is clear that these movements occur in low Reynolds number flows. In this paper, first, we are going to introduce bacterial motion and physics behind bacterial motility. Since most bacteria use flagella for movement, the main focus of this paper is on flagellar motion, the mechanics and dynamics that lies behind it. In this respect, the fluid mechanics of the fluid environment that bacteria move through is of high significance.

Therefore, the mechanics of flows in which bacteria moves will be examined. After that, the theorem that scientists have proposed to justify bacterial motion will be reviewed. In the final section of the paper, we will go over the application of studying bacterial motion in the creation of artificial micro-swimmers and their application in today's world.

2. Properties of low Reynolds number flows

The most well-known number in fluid mechanics is Reynolds number, by means of which the main flow characteristics can be determined. Reynolds number is a dimensionless number which is defined as the ratio of inertia forces to viscous forces, and it is defined as $Re = \frac{\rho UL}{\mu}$, where U and L are characteristic velocity and length, and ρ and μ are density and kinematic viscosity. In this respect, when Reynolds number is less than one, the flow is known as low Reynolds flow. In low Reynolds flows, the effect of inertia is minimal and unimportant. Inertia is defined as the willingness of an object to maintain its current condition, whether it's moving or not unless some force is exerted on it. Therefore, when we say an object has a small inertia, it means that it can be moved easily or it can be stopped from moving instantaneously. On the other hand, if we assume an object which is moving with a large inertia due to an external force, the object will still resume its motion for a while after the force is removed. Viscosity is the resistance of the fluid to flow. Unlike inertia, that tries to keep the motion of a moving object, viscosity attempts to stop the object. The effect of inertia can be clearly demonstrated by comparing the swimming of a bacteria and a whale. For a whale that swims with a speed of 10 m/s, the Reynolds number is in the order of 10^8 , while for a bacteria (swimming at a speed of around 0.01 mm/s), the Reynolds number is in the order of 10^{-5} . As mentioned before, since the inertia forces are not important in low Reynolds flow, the bacteria can immediately stop or change direction, whereas the whale will still "coast" for a long distance after it stops swimming [4].

According to calculations done by Purcell, things move in water that has a kinematic viscosity of 0.01 cm²/sec at a speed of about 30 μ m/sec. Interestingly enough, if we assume that we can stop the moving object by removing the force, it only takes the object 0.6 μ sec to stop, that is because of the dominancy of viscous forces. A very interesting definition by Purcell about low Reynolds flows is when you are at low Reynolds, the forces that are important are the ones that are on you "at the moment" not the past. As he indicates, swimming in low Reynolds number can be illustrated by imagining yourself trying to swim in in a pool of molasses [5].

Let us now bring the Navier-Stokes equation that describes the fluid flow of viscous flows into play:

$$\frac{\partial \vec{u}}{\partial t} + (\vec{u} \cdot \nabla) \vec{u} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla P + \frac{\mu}{\rho} \nabla^2 \vec{u} \quad (1)$$

where \vec{u} is the velocity vector and P is the pressure. As introduced in many texts and paper, the first term from the left is the time-dependent inertial component which would be zero if the flow is steady.

The second term on the left-hand side of the equation is the non-linear inertial term. The terms on the right-hand side of the equation are pressure gradient and viscous dissipation terms, respectively. We can non-dimensionalize the equation in order to analyze the effect of inertia and viscous forces mathematically. Let us scale \vec{u} with U , the spatial derivative ∇ with $\frac{1}{L}$, and time t with $\frac{L}{U}$. By doing so, the first term of the equation would be something in the order of $\frac{U^2}{L}$, the non-linear inertia term is in the order of $\frac{U^2}{L}$, and the viscous term is in the order of $\frac{\mu U}{\rho L^2}$. Therefore, the ratio of the inertia to the viscous terms is $\frac{\rho U L}{\mu}$, that is another representation of Reynolds number. Since in low Reynolds number flows we have $Re \ll 1$, we can say that the equation would turn out to be:

$$0 = -\nabla P + \mu \nabla^2 \vec{u} \quad (2)$$

This equation is called Stokes equation. Stokes equation has its particular characteristics. First of all, it is a time-dependent equation, meaning that if the boundary conditions are known for a Stokes flow, the flow field can be solved. Linearity is the second property of Stokes equation. Since the equation is linear, any forces that is applied to the flow would be followed by a response from the flow. Stokes equation is also time-reversible, which is a result of instantaneity. This means that the equations that Stokes flow solves are the same ones as the ones that can be solved by the time-reversed Stokes flow [4].

The motion of micro-organisms, that happens by movements of flagella or cilia as we mentioned before, are known as periodic motions. Thus, a different way of scaling the Navier-Stokes equation can be performed. This time, the characteristic time scale T can be used and therefore velocity would be scaled as $\frac{L}{T}$, in which L is the characteristic length. The inertial terms and the viscous terms should also be scaled as $\frac{L}{T^2}$ and $\frac{\mu}{\rho L T}$, respectively. The ratio of inertia and viscous forces can be then expressed as $\frac{\rho L^2}{\mu T}$, which is a dimensionless number known as Stokes number or periodic flow Reynolds number. Yet, we will reach the same equation as we reached by the first scaling method if the flow is Stokes flow or in low Reynolds. To summarize, in a low Reynolds number flow, viscous forces dominate. Also, flow is almost always laminar and no flow separation occurs. Furthermore, flow is reversible and no coasting of the moving object happens [4].

When we have a deformable swimming animal, we can assume that we have no-slip boundary condition, which means the velocity of the fluid at the surface of the animal body is equal to the velocity of the animal body. It is worth mentioning that the Reynolds number for micro-organisms is typically way less than 1. However, Reynolds number vary with the kind of micro-organisms. For instance, E-Choli

moves with a Reynolds of around $10^{-5} - 10^{-4}$, while Paramecium, which is a micro-organism with bigger cilia moves with Reynolds of about 0.1 [5].

3. Mechanics and dynamics of swimming in low Reynolds

Purcell defines swimming as a non-zero asymptotic deformation of the body, in which the only force or torque that is exerted on the body of the swimmer is the one that is exerted by the viscous fluid. As can be seen in Figure 1, drawn by Purcell, the object moves and moves back and therefore, a cycle is created, as a result of which displacement occurs. Thus, swimming is a cycle. An example of cyclic motion is called reciprocal motion, in which the form of the body changes and then it changes back to its initial form by going reversely in the same direction. However, it can be proved that these deformation does not lead to displacement in low Reynolds number flow because it heads back to its original position, even if the animal does the changes so fast. In fact, in low Reynolds number flows we will be left with $\nabla^2 V = \frac{P}{\eta}$. This means that a scallop is not able to move in low Reynolds number either because it only has one hinge or it just opens and closes which is a reciprocal motion [5].

Figure 2 derived from [5], Cyclic motion of a theoretical animal. The animal comes back to its initial position after a cycle

Purcell suggested that if an animal wants to swim in low Reynolds flows, it has to have two degrees of freedom. A hypothetical animal that is capable of swimming using its two hinges was suggested by him and is shown in Figure 2. This swimmer has two rudders at both of its ends and the rudders go through a loop of movements which leads to animal's displacement [5].

Figure 3 derived from [5], A hypothetical swimmer that has a degree of freedom of two. It performs a cyclic motion, but since the cycle is not reciprocal, there will be a net displacement after each cycle.

Other solutions that Purcell had inferred for the swimming problem are called the flexible oar and the corkscrew. In the flexible oar solution that can be seen in Figure 3 the flexibility of the oar helps it to bend from its one side during the first half of its motion and bend from its other side during the second half of the motion. This mechanism results in the animal displacement [5].

The flexible oar

The corkscrew

Figure 4 derived from [5], two more solutions to the swimming problem that were suggested by Purcell. Both of these models exhibit non-reciprocal motions and therefore have the potential to swim in low Reynolds flow

Both of the abovementioned structures does not do the reciprocal motion. Howard Berg sketched a picture of some micro-organisms that he studied, Figure 4. He suggested that *S. Volutans* uses its spirally waving body to swim. E-Choli, however, has a tail that is 2μm long which is called flagella [5].

Figure 5 derived from [5], schematic picture of three different types of bacteria that was drawn by Howard berg

A solid body in low Reynolds will move if a force is exerted on it. Such body moves with a velocity of U and rotation rate of Ω if force F and torque L is exerted. Therefore, the following equation of matrices can be written for the motion:

$$\begin{pmatrix} F \\ L \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ B^T & C \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} U \\ \Omega \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

By re-writing the equation in terms of U and Ω , we will have:

$$\begin{pmatrix} U \\ \Omega \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} M & N \\ N^T & O \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} F \\ L \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

This equation is called mobility equation, which has to be symmetric due to reciprocal theorem. Some other characteristics are required for the equations to justify the body displacement. First of all, the equations should be drag anisotropic that is a required condition for a body to move at zero Reynolds. This means that the matrices A , M , C , O do not have to be isotropic. An example of drag anisotropy is a spheroid under gravity force. If the spheroid is not perfectly perpendicular to the orientation of gravity, the spheroid sediments along its length with a constant angle that its velocity vector makes with the direction of gravity. The second property of the equations is that they explain driving translational motion if the body of the swimmer does not have a mirror symmetry plane (when matrices B and N are non-zero). This is why bacteria with rotating helical flagella swim. Moreover, these equations can be used to calculate the diffusion constants of solid bodies (D) [6].

As we know, Stokes equation is linear and it may be solved for the pressure and the velocity of the flow field. Lauga et al [6] suggested Green function (G) for Stokes flow, which is a tensor that is multiplied by force to give us the velocity. G is also called Oseen's tensor and the solution to this equation is called Stokeslet. Stokeslet shows the flow field that occurs when a force F is exerted on the fluid at the point x' . Solving for the Stokeslet solution we will see that the velocity of the flow field for the same exerted force when the direction of the velocity is parallel to the exerted force is twice as of that when the direction of the velocity is perpendicular to the direction of the exerted force. In brief, it can be said that $u_{\parallel} = 2u_{\perp}$ and $F_{\perp} = 2F_{\parallel}$. This fact, which is similar to the anisotropy in the mobility matrix, is the base for drag-based propulsion method which is employed by some swimming micro-organisms [6].

4. Another interpretation of Reynolds number

Lauga et al [6] suggested that there is a relation between the distance that the swimmer coasts and Reynolds number. Consider m and L as mass and size of the swimmer which swims with the velocity U in the fluid with density and viscosity of ρ and μ . Imagine the swimmer stops deforming its body all of a sudden and therefore stops swimming after a certain distance, d. Thus, the swimmer decelerates for a certain distance to completely stop. If we assume that the magnitude of deceleration is a, then we will have:

$$ma = F_{drag} \quad (5)$$

If the swimmer is like a human which swims in high Reynolds, the inertial force is going to be somewhat equal to drag force: $f_{drag} \sim f_{inertia} \sim \rho L^2 U^2$ which means that the magnitude of deceleration is: $a \sim \rho L^2 U^2 / m$ and therefore, the distance that the swimmer coasts is $d \sim m / (\rho L^2)$. If the density of swimmer is $\rho_s \sim m / L^3$. By comparing ρ_s and d we can see that $\rho / \rho_s \sim d / L$, which means that the dimensionless coasting distance is found by the dimensionless density. However, the case is a little bit different in low Reynolds number flows, because inertia is not important and we have $f_{drag} \sim f_{viscous} \sim \eta UL$ and therefore the coasting distance can have such correlation with Reynolds number: $d / L \sim Re^{\rho_s / \rho}$. Hence, we can see that the Reynolds number was interpreted as the dimensionless coasting distance [4]. These findings can be summarized within the fact that the change in the momentum of the swimmer in low Reynolds flow is negligible compared to the magnitude of the forces exerted to the swimmer by the flow (viscous forces). Thus, balance between the forces would be $F_{ext} + F_t = 0$ and $L_{ext} + L_t = 0$. The external forces and torques are typically zero and therefore the forces and torques of the flow are zero as well [6].

5. Drag-based thrust and Purcell's theorem

Let us focus on the most common mechanism that is employed by micro-organisms for swimming, which is called drag-based thrust. Drag-based thrust is created by flagella or cilia's motion and results in the locomotion. The drag anisotropy of the slender filaments make the drag-based thrust to be likely to happen. However, drag anisotropy is not enough itself and two conditions are required for the thrust to happen. First, drag anisotropy should exist which makes propulsive forces probable to be created. The direction of the filaments' motion creates a right angle with these propulsive forces. The second condition is the periodic deformation as well as non-zero time averaged propulsion of the filament. For slender filaments, there are local drag forces which oppose the filament's motion. This force can be defined as the following:

$$\mathbf{f} = -\xi_{\parallel}\mathbf{u}_{\parallel} - \xi_{\perp}\mathbf{u}_{\perp} \quad (6)$$

which depends on the drag coefficients and local velocity projections of the filament. If the drag is isotropic, then $\xi_{\parallel} = \xi_{\perp}$ and the direction of the velocity of the filament and the force on the filament are the same. Nevertheless, if $\xi_{\parallel} \neq \xi_{\perp}$, the propulsive force is then perpendicular to the velocity direction. Figure 5 shows the schematic of the local velocity, forces, and drag of a swimmer [6].

Figure 6 derived from [6], Illustrates that drag anisotropy should exist in order for the propulsive force to happen. If drag forces get cancelled by velocity vectors, there will be no propulsive force and therefore no displacement

Therefore, locomotion cannot take place if $\xi_{\parallel} = \xi_{\perp}$, which is when we have isotropic viscous forces. Also, in order to have non-zero time-averaged forces, the movement of filament should occur in a non-time reversal fashion. The abovementioned concept is known as Purcell's theorem [6].

6. Scallop theorem

Linearity and time-dependency of Stokes equation lead to two significant results. The first conclusion is that the distance that is travelled by a swimmer that deforms its body does not depend on the rate of motion but depends only on the geometry of deformations. The second result is what is known as scallop theorem, which was partly touched in the previous section. This theorem indicates that in low Reynolds is not possible with reciprocal motion. In other words, if the order of the motions that going forward and backward are the same by reversing time, the swimmer is not able to move [6].

7. A simple three linked spheres swimmer (Golestanian Swimmer) [2]

As we mentioned before, Purcell showed that animals such as a scallop that have one degree of freedom cannot swim because their motion is reversible and in fact, they go back to where they initially were before the cycle of their motion, and therefore, no displacement takes place. Purcell also suggested that the animal needs to do a non-reciprocal motion, which is not time-reversibly symmetric, in order to be able to swim. According to his paper, this kind of motion leads to animal displacement, which occurs due to self-propulsion of the animal in some direction. The direction is determined by the symmetry of the system and motion. Although the hypothetical swimmer that he suggested is simple in terms of geometry, the quantitative analysis is so complicated that cannot be easily solved. Najafi and Golestanian introduced a simple and accessible swimmer based on Purcell's model with little changes, which is able to swim using periodical internal motions. The model is comprised of three spheres in the same axis that are connected together with two rigid slender arms. The spheres should be floated in a flow with high viscosity. The idea is to make the non-reciprocal motion. Thus, the middle sphere is assumed to have two internal engines, by the help of which the self-propulsion movement of the system is possible. The proposed cyclic motion consists of four steps that are going to be explained in the following [2]:

1. In the first step of the motion, the length of the left arm decreases by one of the engines of the middle sphere. The length of the right arm however does not change in the first step.
2. In the second step, the other engine of the middle sphere decreases the length of the right arm with the same velocity as the first step.
3. In the third step, the length of the right arm increases by the internal engine of the middle sphere to reach the original length. The left arm however is kept fixed.

4. The last step is the increase in the length of the left arm to put the left sphere back to where it initially was.

All the four steps are done with the same speed. The researchers hypothesized that if the cycle is repeated continuously, a translational motion will occur. As discussed before, we use the Stokes equation to describe the hydrodynamics of the motion in low Reynolds flows:

$$0 = -\nabla P + \mu \nabla^2 \vec{u} \quad (7)$$

$$\nabla \cdot u = 0 \quad (8)$$

where p and u are the pressure and velocity fields, respectively [2].

Figure 7 derived from [2], three linked spheres that perform four steps in order to travel for a displacement magnitude of Δ . The middle sphere employs two internal engines to apply changes in the lengths of the arms

The equation can be solved using no-slip boundary condition and zero velocity at infinity. Let us assume V_i and F_i the fluid velocity and force of the fluid on sphere number i . These two variables are required to be obtained in order to solve the motion. This means that if we can obtain the fluid velocity and the stress tensor, we can find the forces on the spheres easily. Since the governing of motion and stress tensor equations are linear, the form of the velocity would easily be:

$$V_i = \sum_{j=1}^3 H_{ij} \cdot F_j \quad (9)$$

in which H_{ij} is the Oseen tensor that depends on the viscosity of the media's fluid and the geometry of the system. An important assumption here is no force such as gravity is applied to the spheres and therefore, the spheres are force-free:

$$\sum_{j=1}^3 F_j = 0 \quad (10)$$

Now the equations 9 and 10 can be solved instead of the governing equations because the hydrodynamics of the motion is the point of interest. In order to solve the equations 9 and 10, the researchers used an auxiliary move. We are not going to explain the process of solving the equation, and we close this section by outlining the results of their calculations and findings.

The first conclusion is that the body swimming velocity depends on the velocity of the internal motion, which can mean that the velocity of the swimmer can potentially be controlled. Furthermore, the small deformations in the system (changing position by the spheres through the cycle) have a quadratic effect on the velocity of the swimmer. These two conclusions are based on the mathematical correlation that was found by the researchers. These consequences can be shown in the mathematical correlation that was found in this study for the velocity of the swimmer:

$$V_s = 0.7W \cdot \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \left(\frac{\epsilon}{D}\right)^2 \quad (11)$$

in which W , R , D , ϵ are the constant velocity of the internal motion, the radius of spheres, the original length of the arms, and the displacement of each side sphere in the first two steps, respectively [2].

Besides, the researchers suggested that the right and left spheres move towards the middle sphere. This is to collapse the time-reversal symmetry condition, with which the non-reciprocal motion occurs. In order for the cycle to be continuously periodic, the phase difference between periodic motions of the two side spheres should be non-zero with respect to the middle sphere [2].

Overall, a swimmer that is able to perform self-propulsion motion has been introduced by Najafi and Golestanian, called Golestanian swimmer. In brief, the idea is to break the time-reversal and translational symmetry using continuous periodic motion. The model can be employed in desired machines or devices in micro-scale as the swimmer is able to swim in low Reynolds flows. The other benefits of this model are the fact that the analysis of its hydrodynamics is easy and therefore the swimmer can swim in a controllable fashion [2].

8. Artificial micro-swimmer robots

Artificial micro-swimmers are the micro-devices whose designs are inspired by micro-organisms' swimming mechanisms. For instance, Ghanbari et al [7] designed a micro-swimmer that is inspired by ciliated micro-organism and has the potential to be employed in both viscous and turbulent flows with a maximum speed of 4.5 mm/s and efficiency (In this context, efficiency means the ratio of the useful to the rate of total work of the swimmer against viscous fluid) of 40%. Micro-swimmers application in medical technologies is growing rapidly since they are able to perform free moves in the human body and can even be used for difficult surgical applications.

Lauga et al [6] have categorized the different designs of micro-swimmers that have been developed so far to three main categories: First are the group of swimmers who perform a non-reciprocal motion by deforming their body by the help of a finite number of degrees of freedom, at least two. For example, the Golestanian swimmer that we just discussed is of this kind of swimmers. Besides, researchers have suggested designs with two spheres. As other scientists have proposed and Lauga et al [6] have reported, net propulsion can be achieved even if the shapes of the system perform individual reciprocal motions. This is because the interactions between the bodies of the systems have the potential to create a net propulsion. It has also been ascertained that the distance between the swimmers, and their positioning and location influence the resulting swimming motion [6].

The second type of artificial micro-swimmers swims by performing continuous body deformations. This kind of micro-swimmers is also expanded to different types. A great example of this type of micro-swimmer is the one that has been designed by a group of researchers in Drexel University, Philadelphia. This micro robot contains a chain of magnetic particles and its motion can be controlled by external magnetic fields. This tiny robot swims through the bloodstream. Since human's artery is so slim it sometimes clogs up which causes diseases. The complexity and the risk of surgical operations are high and mini-robots that can be injected into patient's artery can be helpful in this context. The design of this micro-swimmer is inspired from one of Purcell's solutions to the swimming problem, which is a corkscrew-like design. This micro-swimmer is typically 200 nm to 10 μm in size. They can be manipulated through blocked artery and ease the surgical operation. They are also able to deliver drugs in the desired and targeted location very precisely. However, further research is required to achieve a point that this micro-swimmer is employed in real surgeries [8].

Figure 8 derived from [8], the red and blue lines show the direction of a micro-swimmer that is invented recently

Figure 9 derived from [8], Corkscrew shape of an artificial micro-swimmer

The third type of artificial micro-swimmers uses chemical reactions to perform their motions. The swimmer that is experimentally investigated by researchers contains two materials, an inert and a reactant/catalyst chemical to fulfill the chemical reaction. The concentration gradient that is created due to the presence of some reactants/products of the chemical reaction results in slip velocities at the fluid-particle interface [6].

9. Conclusion

In this paper, we tried to introduce a relatively novel field of study, bacterial locomotion, which was first studied by Purcell. We first briefly explained the possible mechanisms for bacterial locomotion. We continued our study by focusing on flagellum motion, and introduced the environments in which they swim, low Reynolds number flows. We then analyzed the characteristics of low Reynolds flow and explained how the dimensional analysis is done on Navier-Stokes equation, Stokes equation, and Reynolds number. After that, the mechanics and dynamics of the bacterial motion and the possible solutions to swimming problem and clarified the conditions should be met for an animal to be able to swim in low Reynolds. Scallop theorem and Purcell theorem which are the main theories in this context were explained afterward. Since many parameters and reasons contribute to swimming of micro-organisms, a plethora of topics and considerations such as various hydrodynamic interactions and physical actuations have been reviewed and studied by different researchers. However, we confined our study to review drag-based thrust which is why flagellum motion occurs. A simple theoretical swimmer,

called Golestanian swimmer that has less complexity compared to other suggested swimmers was then introduced and the results of the studies were explained. In the last section of the paper, we studied the applications of artificial micro-swimmers, the designs of which are inspired by bacterial locomotion. Also, different types of artificial micro-swimmers were briefly introduced.

Bibliography

- [1] Flow analysis of the low-Reynolds number swimmer *C. elegans*, Thomas D. Montenegro-Johnson, David A. Gagnon, Paulo E. Arratia, and Eric Lauga
- [2] Simple swimmer at low Reynolds number: Three linked spheres Ali Najafi and Ramin Golestanian
- [3] <https://microbiologybytes.wordpress.com/2008/06/02/bacterial-motility/>
- [4] Low Reynolds number flows, chapter written by Daniel Bershader, obtained from <http://www.fem.unicamp.br/index.php/pt-br/>
- [5] Life at low Reynolds number, E. M. Purcell, Citation: American Journal of Physics 45, 3 (1977); doi: 10.1119/1.10903
- [6] The hydrodynamics of swimming microorganisms, Eric Lauga and Thomas R Powers
- [7] A Novel Swimming Micro robot Based on Artificial Cilia for Biomedical Applications, Ali Ghanbari, Mohsen Bahrami
- [8] <https://www.netexplo.org/en/intelligence/innovation/micro-swimmer-robot>